

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 24th October 2022
Accepted: 01st November 2022
Online: 04th November 2022

KEY WORDS

Pedagogues , ages, memory , permanent memory , language learners , kids , teenagers , adults , exircises ,main goal , visual knesetic , auditory , skills, an effective lesson

We know that learning has no age limit. Including language learning. But Memory begins to fade after you are older and learning becomes more difficult. And this has a some negative effect on language learning. "How can we make the lesson more effective and achieve a good result?", "How can I make the lesson more understandable for the learner?", "What exercises should I choose?" Such questions are troubled many teachers.

The solution to such questions is that we, the future pedagogues, need to group learners in the process of language teaching. We need to group learners based on their age, level of knowledge and what type of learner they are. Firstly, we divide the learner into groups based on their age. At schools they are grouped by age, but at university and additional language courses, this is not given much attention, and this can lead to a deterioration in the quality of the lesson. Because people of all ages do not think similarly. They have very

HOW TO TEACH MORE EFFECTIVELY

Xurramova Sarvinoz Farhod qizi

Assisuyunov@gmail.com

Termiz State University

303-group foreign philology faculty

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7287857>

ABSTRACT

This article deal with ways of teaching more effectively and tecaher how to create their teaching atmosphere. In this article is used from methodology books. And it includes some real examples and some games.

different worldviews in terms of their age. Learners are divided their ages into kids (3-12-ages), teenagers(12-25-ages) and adults(older than 25 age). In fact children have a very strong memory, they immediately remember what they see and hear then keep it in their permanent memory. But they remember only simple and easy things. That is, they remember only the things around their thinking circle. In addition, they are more playful and do not look at life realistically. Therefore, it is necessary to use more colorful pictures in the process of teaching language. For example, using from picture books or exercises with pictures of flowers, animals, birds, songs and poems suitable for young people, interesting and funny games, in addition to through encouraging them, they can be taught very quickly and easily. For example, a game called "touch". This game can be adapted by the teacher to the topic of his choice. The theme may be "human body parts". Firstly, the teacher introduces

the children to the human body parts and writes down the translation and explains it on the example of a child. Then he tells the children in English name of the body parts and the children should touch that body part. The child who made a mistake loses and leaves the game. At the end, the last 3 children are given gifts by the teacher. In such games, the child quickly memorizes without knowing it and keeps it in permanent memory. Using of which game and in which situation depend on the skill of the teacher.

How to teach teenagers more effectively?

I think teaching teenagers is a bit more difficult (that's just my opinion). Because they are clueless and see the world differently than others. Even their character can be prevent from their study. They have a strong inner "I", they have a changeable character. Therefore, we should approach them with some caution and gentleness in the process of teaching them. They don't like your criticisms and childish attitude and they start avoiding your lessons and at the same time they lose interest. The subject you are teaching should be interesting, understandable and relevant to them. You cannot apply games or gifts to them. It's more effective to make your teaching simpler and a little more interesting by relating the subject you're teaching to a real-life situation they often encounter or may encounter. For example, You show them scenes from funny movies or use exercises with funny situations.

Teaching adults is a little easier and doesn't require you to be creative. It basically requires more knowledge and skills from you. Because adults have a main reason for learning a language and have specific goals. They are not just interested in some kind of achievement through learning they want

to achieve something. For example, to become a student, to increase their salary, or to work and live in a foreign country. That is why they take language learning seriously. They try not to spend too much time. This requires a lot of knowledge and skill from you. They focus on most factual, the big topics they need to learn and its small details. But they have memory problems, so you have to work with them more and more accurately. For example, should they learn grammar, they just try to learn it better. They are not interested in the pronunciation of words, synonyms, antonyms.

Secondly, you need to group according to the learner's level of knowledge. Language learners are divided into several levels based on state standards: beginner, elementary, pre-intermediate, upper intermediate, advanced. How can you determine this? You can determine this through tests that determine the language level. And you use words, phrases, grammatical topics at that level. Special study books for this grade have been prepared to make your task easier. Your task is to choose the best and the most correct of them and using from additional exercises. Or you can collect information from several of them and combine them to make it simpler to teach the learner.

Thirdly, you need to determine what type of learner your learners are. Learners are mainly divided into 3 types: visual, kinesthetic and auditory.

A) Visual learners learn by seeing and touching You use charts, graphs, pictures, slides and powerpoints for teaching.

B) Knesetic learners learn by doing physical activities. You use part of some stories or movies. You teach with acting or doing some acts.

C) Auditorial learners learn by listening. They also can learn not seeing and touching. They listen and they remember what it is. You use verbal dialogs, conversations, some musics, teaching vedios and listenning tasks.

Clarifying the type of learner can also help improve the effectiveness of your teaching. At the same time, it facilitates the process of studying.

In short, all of these things will help your teaching process to be enjoyable and high-quality, and your teaching experience will increase. Your main goal: "Why do you teach this?, What do you teach this? and How do you teach this?"

After grouping them, how you teach to them depends on your skill and knowledge.

You create the learning environment by yourself. We know that every teacher has his own way of teaching. It also has to do with their character.

Just because you are a teacher does not mean that you can teach every lesson that is equally understandable to everyone. You can only provide quality lessons for a certain age level or a certain type of learner. You can teach others but it will not be effective either you will not give them enough knowledge or they will not perform well.

In order to have an effective lesson, you need to choose your way and your learners correctly. It's not difficult, you are the group or young pedagogue whose group of students shows good results.

References:

1. Bekmuratova U. B. Abstract on "Using innovative technologies in teaching English". Tashkent - 2012
2. Otaboeva, M. R. The use of modern innovative technologies in foreign language teaching and its effectiveness / M. R. Otaboeva. — Text: neposredstvennyy, elektronnyy // Molodoy uchenyy. — 2017. — No. 4.2 (138.2). — S. 36–37. — URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/138/39058/> (data processing: 04/27/2020)
3. N. Q. Khatamova, M. N. Mirzayeva. "INTERACTIVE METHODS USED IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE LESSONS" (methodical guide), Navoi, 2006, 40 pages.
4. M. Kholdorova, N. Fayziyeva, F. Rikhsittilayeva. "USE OF HELPING TOOLS IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE". Tashkent: TDPU named after Nizomi, 2005
5. O'Hashimov, I. Yakubov. "ENGLISH TEACHING METHODOLOGY" (study guide) Tashkent: "Sharq" publishing house, 2003.